

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“NAPUSGAY’NG KASING-KASING”

Ayaw ko’g binli’g samad
Ayaw ko’g ibilin sa ulan
Balika dad-a mga pahiyom
wad-ang mga luha ko
Mga bukton mo gaksa ako
Tampalasang kagabhion
Ibalik gapauraray’ng mga takna

Napusgay’ng kasing-kasing ko
Isugilon gugma mo
Alimaha ang samad sa adlaw
sa imong pagbiya kanako
Pahiri ki’ng mga luha
Gabangutan ako
Gipusgay mo kasing-kasing ko

Bakwiang panamilit
Ibalik kalipay’g hudyaka
Ayaw ko’g binli sa mga luha
Hagki’ng kasakit ni’ng dughan
Ang pagbiya mo di malimtan
Mapuangurong takna
Ay kasubo gyud ang pag-inusara

Ayaw ko’g binli’g samad
Ayaw ko’g ibilin sa ulan
Ibalik gapauraray’ng mga takna
Napusgay’ng kasing-kasing ko
Isugilon gugma mo

Alimaha ang samad sa adlaw
sa imong pagbiya kanako
Pahiri mga luha ko
Gabangutan ako
Gipusgay mo kasing-kasing ko

Isugilon ang gugma mo
Ayaw ko'g biyai
Ayaw ko'g talikdi
Isugilon ang gugma mo
Ayaw ko'g duslaka sakit kaayo

Categories

Please **HIGHLIGHT** the category that best fits your submission:

- ◆ Poetry
- ◆ Short Stories
- ◆ Essays

- ◆ **Spotlight on Emerging Writers**
- ◆ **Creative Corner**
- ◆ **Others:** _____ (Please specify)

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